

Pant Dhan 4, Pant Dhan 10, and Pant Dhan 12) at two N fertility levels.

The experiment was conducted in the 1994 and 1995 wet seasons at Pantnagar, where the soil is a silt loam (Aquic Hapludoll) with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, 0.1 % total N, and CEC 20 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. N level (120 and 160 kg N ha⁻¹) was in the main plot and varieties (PRH-1, Jaya, Pant Dhan 4, Pant Dhan 10, and Pant Dhan 12) in the subplots. A single basal dose of 17.5 kg P ha⁻¹, 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹, and 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ was uniformly applied in all plots. N was applied as per treatment in three splits: 1/2 as basal, 1/4 topdressed at active tillering, and 1/4 topdressed at panicle initiation. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 7 Jul in both years at 20- × 20-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings hill⁻¹.

Varieties did not respond differently to N. An additional dose of 40 kg N (bringing total N to 160 kg ha⁻¹) helped plants yield 7% more grain than at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ the recommended dose for high-yielding inbreds. The difference, however, was not significant (see table).

Hybrid rice PRH-1 yielded significantly more (17% in 1994 and 13% in 1995) than the best-performing inbreds: Jaya (12% less), Pant Dhan 4 (17% less), Pant Dhan 10 (19% less), and Pant Dhan 12 (15% less).

Based on these findings, suitable hybrids can produce 15-20% more than today's best inbred varieties in intensive input systems. ■

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

FKR42 and FKR44: irrigated rice varieties released to farmers in Burkina Faso

M. Sie, Y. Sere, and A. Sanou, Institut d' études et de recherche agricoles (INERA), station de Farako-Bâ, 01 BP 910, Bobo-Dioulasso, 01 Burkina Faso, West Africa

Rice varieties IR64 and IR13240-108-2-2-3 were introduced into INERA's breeding program through collaboration with the International Network for

Genetic Evaluation of Rice and the West Africa Rice Development Association.

Both varieties proved promising in advanced yield trials in 1992-95 (see table). They also performed well in adaptive on-farm trials under farmers' cultural practices.

The varieties are early-maturing with long, slender grains and are suited for irrigated rice - rice double cropping. Both were released in 1995: IR64 as FKR42 (Farako-Bâ Riz) and IR13240-108-2-2-3 as FKR44. ■

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) in irrigated rice variety trials^a at the INERA research stations in the Kou and Sourou valleys, Burkina Faso. 1992-95 wet (WS) and dry seasons (DS).

Variety	Kou Valley				Sourou Valley	
	1992 WS	1993 DS	1994 WS	1995 DS	1994 WS	1995 DS
IR64 (FKR42)	4.3	4.3	4.0	2.4	6.1	6.9
IR13240-108-2-2-3 (FKR44)	—	—	4.7	2.8	—	7.7
ITA123 (FKR28)	4.1	2.1	4.3	3.0	3.2	7.7
4456 (FKR16)	4.1	3.1	4.4	2.9	5.4	6.6

^aFertilizer rate = 88-69-42 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

Integrated germplasm improvement — upland

Evaluating local germplasm for the upland rice ecosystem in western Nepal

K. D. Joshi, Local Initiatives for Biodiversity, Research and Development, Pokhara, Nepal; B. R. Sthapit, Nepal Agriculture Research Council, Khumaltar, Nepal

Upland rice, locally known as *ghaiya dhan* in Nepal, is grown as the major crop in the *tars* (unirrigated ancient river fans), on terraced lands, and on hills where forests have recently been cleared. Most of the 126,000 ha (9% of the country's total rice area) under *ghaiya* is hilly. Resource-poor upland farmers from ethnic groups such as the Kumal, Derai, and Bote are the main growers of this rice.

Of the 42 rice varieties released in Nepal, only *Ghaiya 2* (MV10) is suitable for subtropical upland areas. Hill farmers, however, do not like it because it is

short and does not perform well under fertility.

Indigenous *ghaiya* varieties have not been properly studied or used in variety development programs that could benefit large farming communities.

Researchers at the Lumle Agricultural Research Center have done some preliminary work on evaluating local germplasm. They screened 53 *ghaiya* land races from Gorkha and Tanahun districts and evaluated them in replicated randomized complete block designs in a target environment (Chyanglitar, 400 m) for two seasons. The crop was broadcast and grown using farmers' practices, except for maintaining a row spacing of 15 cm between the entries. Farmers were involved in ranking the varieties at maturity. *Ghaiya* varieties that performed poorly during the first year were dropped. Only 24 varieties were tested during the second season.

Table 1. Variability in 53 Ghaiya varieties for different traits.

Character	Range	Mean	SD	SE
Leaf length (cm)	16-85	50.2	9.77	0.42
Leaf width (cm)	1-2.6	1.61	0.25	0.01
Leaves tallest tiller ⁻¹ (no.)	4-8	5.58	0.85	2.22
Internode length (cm)	29-47	38.57	3.0	0.29
Culms (no.)	1-14	4.99	2.39	0.10
Plant height (cm)	80-156	133.0	11.28	1.10
Panicle length (cm)	20.3-28	24.59	1.49	0.15
Grains tallest tillers ⁻¹ (no.)	3-332	110.2	50.97	0.04

Indigenous ghaiya varieties have a large leaf area, which may have important implications for drought tolerance. Because of its tall, weak architecture, the plant commonly lodges under high fertility. The varieties showed variability in traits contributing to yield potential (such as panicle length, amount of grain, and leaf number on the tallest tiller) and other traits (such as leaf characteristics and internode length) that are important for varietal improvement programs (Table 1).

The study revealed that there was a lot of variation for grain yield. The majority of indigenous ghaiya varieties were at par with semidwarf rice variety Ghaiya 2 for grain yield (Table 2). At maturity, local farmers helped assess the phenotypic acceptance of the rice entries. They rated the majority of entries as good to excellent, with most of the entries having plant height and maturity periods suitable for local conditions.

The study identified variability between and within different genotypes that can be used both for developing varieties through pureline selection and in crossing programs. Although farmers are only growing these land races in a few places, more could be benefiting from them through participatory variety selection and promotion of them in similar ghaiya-growing areas.

To obtain varieties that are useful for farmers, indigenous knowledge and genetic resources must be tapped to develop high-yielding, suitable ghaiya varieties. ■

Table 2. Performance of Ghaiya varieties at Chyanglitar, Nepal (400 m). 1993-94.

Variety	1993			1994			Phenotypic acceptance 1-9
	Plant height (cm)	Days to maturity	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Plant height (cm)	Days to maturity	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
Kalo Basaune	148	116	3.1	157	124	4.1	3
Kalo Dhan	139	116	3.1	114	123	4.5	4
Sindure Ghaiya	141	116	3.5	143	122	5.4	3
Pahenle Ghaiya	132	113	3.6	142	120	3.6	4
Seto Ghaiya	135	120	3.7	155	123	3.6	4
Bichare	137	112	3.5	143	122	4.4	3
Chobo	132	114	3.4	133	118	3.9	4
Rato Ghaiya	136	117	3.4	144	122	4.5	3
Phalame Chobo	142	112	3.4	149	121	4.0	3
Sano Thantar	138	113	3.5	146	123	3.4	4
Nani Maiya	129	111	3.2	144	121	4.3	3
Pakhe Masino	139	115	3.4	152	124	4.5	3
Phalame Chobo	137	116	3.6	148	118	4.2	4
Nani Dhan	140	114	3.8	139	119	4.4	3
Langre	154	120	4.1	161	125	3.3	2
Jabaka	139	115	3.5	149	120	3.8	4
Begani	134	116	3.3	140	121	3.1	3
Dudhe Tauli	140	113	4.2	150	119	4.2	3
Dare Ghaiya	143	114	2.2	142	121	4.6	2
Chiuri	127	114	2.4	139	120	3.9	4
Jhyalebicharo	140	110	2.8	139	119	4.4	1
Jire Ghaiya	125	121	1.5	144	118	3.4	2
Linde Basaha	138	113	4.2	146	122	4.5	2
Ghaiya 2 (check)	77	125	2.6	85	117	4.9	3
Mean	133	115	2.89	142.9	120.9	4.1	3.08
LSD (0.05)	10.63	4.31	1.16	9.64	2.94	1.09	-

FKR33: a popular upland variety in Burkina Faso

M. Sie, Y. Sere, and A. Sanou, Institut d' études et de recherche agricoles (INERA), station de Farako-Bâ, 01 BP 910, Bobo-Dioulasso, 01 Burkina Faso, West Africa

INERA scientists are developing new promising upland rice varieties from F₄ generations of pedigree lines screened at the Institut des Savanes research station in Bouaké, Côte d'Ivoire. The release of IRAT144 as FKR5 (Farako-Bâ Riz) in Burkina Faso was a result of this collaboration, but the variety has poor grain quality.

In 1982, we developed the line 1119-

5-2 by pedigree selection from the cross IRAT 112/IRAT 13. This variety was released as FKR33 in 1992.

FKR33 matures slightly earlier and is shorter than FKR5. Their grains are of the same length (9.8 mm), but FKR33 grains are more slender (2.8 mm) than that of FKR5 (3.0 mm).

Superior grain type and good head rice recovery are FKR33's best qualities. FKR33 produced 35% more grain than FKR5 in farmers' fields with less than 500 mm of rainfall. In trials conducted in 25 farmers' fields in Comoé Province in southwest Burkina Faso, FKR33's average yield was 3 t ha⁻¹. In Farako-Bâ its yield potential was 6 t ha⁻¹ during the wet season (see table). ■

Agronomic characteristics of upland rice varieties^a, Farako-Bâ Research Station, Burkina Faso. 1992.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Leaf blast ^b	Neck blast ^b	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
FKR5 (IRAT144)	152	107	144	1	1	5.9
FKR33 (1195-5-2)	124	102	228	1	1	6.2
IREM194	162	105	268	3	1	5.9
IDSA13	134	105	128	1	1	5.5

^a Sowing date: 20 Jun 1992; fertilizer rate: 76-46-28 kg NPK ha⁻¹. ^b Scored using the Standard evaluation system for rice. IIRI 1988.